

January 2024

Aneel Bhangu¹

Correspondence: Aneel Bhangu, Editor-in-Chief, Impact Surgery. Email: a.a.bhangu@bham.ac.uk

1. Editor-in-Chief, Impact Surgery

Cite as: Bhangu, A. (2025). January 2025. *Impact Surgery*, 2(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.157>

Thank you very much for helping make Impact Surgery a great success in year 1. We all look forward to 2025! Our key metrics to the end of 2024 are shown below:

- 154 total submissions
- 80% acceptance rate (and falling)
- The 20% rejection rate comprises of a 16% Editor rejection rate and a 4% after review rejection rate
- Median days to First Editorial Decision = median 6 days
- Median days to accept = 16 days
- Top viewed article: Variation of elective healthcare in West Africa: secondary analysis of an inguinal hernia international cohort study (2262 PDF downloads)

We have deepened our website reporting on the journal processes, including peer review, plagiarism checks, and editing processes; we are constantly testing and improving. Crucially, Impact Surgery is embracing an Artificial Intelligence approach to supplement peer review and editing. This involves using a range of Large Language Models in a trial to see how they perform against human reviewers. Each AI review is checked thoroughly by myself. I am also embedding some editing processes into the Generative AI models, and again checking the results carefully. This seems to have lifted some burden off manual peer review.

Our three top viewed articles are:

1. Variation of elective healthcare in West Africa: secondary analysis of an inguinal hernia international cohort study¹.
2. Evaluation of clinical examination and preoperative imaging in patients with right iliac fossa pain and a medium or high risk score for appendicitis (RIFT-2)².
3. Undertaking and writing up a systematic review: a step by step guide³.
4. State of the Art Review: Evidence based management of acute appendicitis⁴.
5. Impact of the ongoing genocide in Gaza on surgical

capacity and healthcare system⁵.

I am keen to support authors who are using ChatGPT and submitting papers written and edited using it. A lot of these authors may not have access to easy writing and editing skills, so I am keen to try and support them. Hopefully, our new papers on how to cite usage of ChatGPT by authors will be useful to the community.

I look forward to 2025. There are some major global challenges, but also great opportunities. I hope you will submit your research to Impact Surgery and we can help you find a good home for it. Please use the templates which you can find as supplements here (<https://www.impact-surgery.org/index.php/pub/article/view/125>)⁶, as it will make publishing faster for you and us.

References

1. Picciochi, M., Agbeko, A. E., & Agyei, F. Variation of elective healthcare in West Africa: secondary analysis of an inguinal hernia international cohort study. *Impact Surgery*. 2024, 1(4), 145–153. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.80>
2. RIFT Study Group. Evaluation of clinical examination and preoperative imaging in patients with right iliac fossa pain and a medium or high risk score for appendicitis (RIFT-2). *Impact Surgery*. 2024, 1(2), 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.34>
3. Naumann, D. Undertaking and writing up a systematic review: a step by step guide. *Impact Surgery*. 2024, 1(4), 154–157. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.71>
4. Kamarajah, S., El Boghdady, M., Anyomih, T., Wohlgemut, J., & Bhangu, A. State of the Art Review: Evidence based management of acute appendicitis. *Impact Surgery*. 2024, 1(2), 35–40. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.45>
5. Alser, O., Asharaf, H. H., & Kishawi, MD, S. Impact of the ongoing genocide in Gaza on surgical capacity and healthcare system : Gaza: impact on surgical capacity. *Impact Surgery*. 2024, 1(3), 73–74.
6. Bhangu, A. Winter Editorial 2024. *Impact Surgery*. 2024, 1(6), 205. <https://doi.org/10.62463/surgery.125>